

LEXICO-SEMANTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF DIPLOMATIC

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6598313>

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Abstract: *This article examines the texts of modern English-language diplomatic correspondence; the subject is the lexical and semantic features of the texts of diplomatic correspondence. The lexical and semantic features of diplomatic correspondence are highlighted, the main translation transformations in the translation of English-language texts of diplomatic correspondence into Uzbek are considered.*

Introduction

A common system of status-role relations that have developed in the communicative space of the social institution of diplomacy can be called diplomatic discourse. It should be viewed as institutional. Mutual communication between addressee and addressee is the core of institutional discourse.

The initial part of the diplomatic documentation of states are documents of an intradepartmental nature. A separate and, perhaps, the most important category can be attributed to documentation through which written official relations between states are made and which express their positions on a number of issues. These documents are written in "diplomatic language". As the name suggests, it is the language in which official diplomatic relations are conducted and negotiations are conducted. It contains phrases, clichés and special terms, the aggregate of which makes up the generally accepted diplomatic vocabulary. The diplomatic style should be distinguished, first of all, by simplicity and clarity. This does not mean the simplicity of the artisan way of expression, but the classical form of simplicity, which knows how to choose for each object the only word that is suitable under the given circumstances, which, for example, avoids the adjective name, when there is no absolute need for the correct transmission of thought. Diplomatic correspondence is one of the main forms of foreign policy and diplomatic activity of a state, since it is a collection of various types of documents of a diplomatic nature and official correspondence through which relations between states are carried out. It is customary to distinguish among the documents of diplomatic correspondence the following genres: personal note, memorandum, memorandum, note verbale. It is obvious that diplomatic discourse has

a kind of agent. Its specificity lies in its group character. According to the definition of diplomacy, agents of diplomatic discourse are represented in two categories. The main category includes representatives of the diplomatic corps and professional diplomats. Professional politicians, that is, senior government officials, represent the second category. The addressee of the diplomatic discourse is no less specific. As well as a rather limited circle of people, namely diplomatic workers of various ranks, and the general public, notified by the media, can act as a client. The character of the client and the agent determines the following feature of the diplomatic discourse, namely its purpose. Informing the general public, both in their own country and abroad, about the point of view of the government of the state they represent on certain international problems is the initial goal of the agent.

The severity and brevity of diplomacy, and, consequently, of diplomatic discourse, obliges the participants to strictly and systematically observe a certain space of freedom of writing. It is unacceptable here to show oneself as an individual person, since a diplomat is a representative of an institution and has a certain status. At the same time, their own opinions and personal characteristics of a person recede into the background.

The main characteristics of the official diplomatic style can be distinguished: 1) high regulation of speech (a certain supply of means of expression and ways of constructing them); 2) impersonality of lexical structures; 3) formality (severity of presentation, words are usually used in their direct meaning, imagery, as a rule, is absent, tropes are very rare). When considering this structure, two sub-styles can be distinguished: official documentary (the language of diplomacy and the language of laws) and everyday business (official correspondence, business papers)

As A.A. Leontiev: "This hierarchy is formed in the speaker on the basis of a certain orientation strategy in the described situation, which depends on the" cognitive weight "of one or another component of the situation." In other words, the presence of a single topic of communication, as well as the presence of the same goal, does not mean that the psychological structure of the situation-topic will be the same in the minds of listeners and speakers, who differ in their psychological characteristics. The linguistic personality of a diplomat stands out in the general structure of diplomatic discourse. The success of all communication is determined by the cognitive, communicative and linguistic abilities of the linguistic personality. In the language of official documents, professionalisms and terms are widely used in accordance with the subject matter and content of official documents. First of all, these are diplomatic, legal and economic terms (business proposal, export, demand, contract, etc.). Words that are mainly used in administrative and clerical speech are also often used (properly, above stated, duly, etc.). It is also a characteristic feature of the use of clerical stamps, reproducible lexicophrasological units, correlating with common concepts and frequently recurring

situations (as discussed, taking into an account, it has been issued, to submit, within reporting period etc.). Business correspondence is replete with complex aberrational prepositions expressing certain standards of content (with regard to, due to, in connection with, etc.) and nouns, namely, the names of people based on an attitude or action (supervisor, manufacturer, consumer, designer, etc.)

Business documents must be translated with great care. Translation transformations are the key to the correct translation of business documents. You need to know and be able to apply various translation techniques. The official business style of documents, in particular diplomatic ones, requires compliance with certain forms of writing a document, adopted in each country. It is necessary to follow the rules of ethics, which include polite forms of contact and the construction of proposals. This style is the most correct style in any language, therefore, deviation from the norms in the design or writing of documents will be perceived as rudeness.

Conclusion.

In the modern world, English has become the language of technology, science and business. In addition, the most important thing is that this language is used when communicating at the international level. The translator must know how to correctly and understandably translate a business document both from Uzbek into English and from English into Uzbek, so that through his fault there is no misunderstanding and incorrect perception of the translated information between business partners. To achieve good results in diplomacy, you need to know not only general English, but also a special one, in our case it is officially business English. Any text in a foreign language is a subject of linguistics study; translation of diplomatic correspondence is also within the range of interests of translators. In this case, linguists and diplomats come into contact. Some do not need to know the peculiarities, subtleties of translation of diplomatic correspondence, while others do not need to know the subtleties and complexity of linguistics.

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